

Remedies of DNA

85 Comments / Blog / By Deepanshu Giri

We all get developed as per our DNA structure, but based on our food habits, our DNA gets energised.

Such as eating spices- Places where most spicy chillies come are usually hot places, and even in states like Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh, local cuisine will incorporate a lot of chillies.

Eating spicy food will not affect the DNA, but it will undoubtedly affect the possibilities encoded in DNA, as Sun represents Nucleus in our DNA structure.

That is why you see the proud communities of Rajasthan/Andhra, and many other such places not able to compromise ever in the principles as constantly eating Spicy food has made them expressive towards their Ego.

The moment you turn towards Gujrat, where the flavour is sweet and a lot of milk products -represent another part of your DNA – which is Sugar and the community thrives largely to travel across the globe and do trade as the Moon is the significator of travel, comforts, happiness as use of low GI food

in regular basis representing Guanine in DNA structure, The community which focuses on expansion of business and whole agenda revolves around the happiness of life and living standards of native as the food continuously expressing through the DNA that emotional and financial well being is important. Jupiter being the significator of banking and finance, is ruled by this state as the expression of DNA is clearly visible.

The Same expression in Rajasthan was visible in being proud of their cultural heritage rather than focusing on business.

It's ok to be born with certain planets, but your food habits affect your DNA to turn off On specific Genetic markers, which play a significant role in Life and Death and how your life will turn out, Food will have a significant impact on your thinking abilities over some time as the food will enable parts of DNA, which will eventually govern your thoughts and at that point of time, if you think by performing specific remedies, you will be able to negate of the thought process and your decision-making capability that is not going to happen.

Most people look for quick fixes in astrology without paying proper attention to their lifestyle, which is why in Lal kitab – There are so many remedies related to food, especially when it comes to Moon or Saturn. Such as, drinking alcohol when Saturn is in the 7th house will have harmful effects on business and married life.

As Saturn represents the Adenine bond of DNA structure – Adenine has the function of increasing the life of Red blood cells, so basically, when the life of Red blood cells grows, It will help you live a longer, healthy and pain-free life; while consuming alcohol will degrade the pool of Adenine, resulting in loss of immunity, it brings out negative fears stored in DNA as now RBC's will start depleting making native to accept situations rather than challenging them.

Let us go to the more practical portion of food and diseases; the picture given below is for Rajasthan from the Indian Council of Medical Research from 1990-2016. The number one diseases in this state is a Lower respiratory infection, and moreover, Rajasthan has trouble with infectious diseases and the easiest way to cure any kind of microbial infection in the body is by generating heat due to Chilli

What caused the most deaths in different age groups in 2016?
Percent contribution of top 10 causes of death by age group, both sexes, 2016

What caused the most years of life lost, by sex, in 2016?
Top 15 causes of YLLs, ranked by percent for both sexes combined, 2016

On the opposite hand, the number of problems or diseases in Gujarat is neurological disorders up to the age of 14 and later on, the problem goes with heart diseases- As spices help to open arteries in the body, which is missing from the food leading to heart-related troubles but the presence of low GI food increased Guanine serving all the other purposes.

You become what you eat, but also how you actually consume your food; the best of the food can be available to us, but if we are not ready to consume food, The same food will react differently with us; every one of us focuses on what we are going to eat but now on how we are going to consume food in our life.

In the lecture of the Moon during Predictive astrology, I specifically mentioned -you can have also paratha without a problem; the problem is when you consume food with the emotion of being conscious of fat, it will definitely create problems for you.

A scientist passed a water bottle to all his students and asked them to say all their negative feelings

to the water; later on, he took that water and froze it; the crystals formed in this particular water were like spikes and unorganised while when the same experiment was conducted by saying all the happy things to water by the same set of students, It resulted in a uniform snowflake structure, now imagine eating food from a hand of the person who is already in stress or while eating you are watching a criminal series, The amount of chemical released by your brain to compensate for the stress is going to make sure the food you are consuming will create spikes in you rather than happiness.

There is enough evidence that food changes the DNA; your DNA is a cosmic storehouse of your Karmas, and you activate your DNA primarily through food; secondly, by the way, we breathe and Nakshatra being the Vayu tatwa is controlled by the food in the first place, By performing Prayanam you are trying to go into a state to activate the DNA portion which is not being utilised as 98% of our is never being used, and this is the same potential of any human which goes waste, called as Junk DNA.

My sincere suggestion to all students of Jyotish is to understand that Grahas are the possibilities in your chart; it is encoded in your DNA; when you chant a particular mantra Phosphate molecule in your DNA gets activated, which in turn helps the nucleus (The power centre) to help you raise your capabilities beyond a certain level.

I will try to write more on this topic as we continue further.

← Previous Post

Next Post →

85 thoughts on “Remedies of DNA”

SREEJA R

3 AUGUST 2023 AT 17:13

A lot of people from Kerala move abroad to the US and Canada. Which placement and food habits will you look for this?